

**ASSESSMENT OF AUTONOMIC DISORDERS IN SCHOOL-AGE
CHILDREN WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA**

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Relevance.

Psycho-emotional stress affects bronchial tone through the autonomic nervous system. Under the influence of psycho-emotional stress, bronchial sensitivity to histamine and acetylcholine increases. Additionally, emotional tension leads to hyperventilation and stimulation of irritant receptors in the bronchi due to sudden deep inhalation, coughing, laughter, or crying, resulting in reflexive bronchial spasms.

Objective.

The aim of this study is to determine the role of psychological status and autonomic homeostasis in the development of bronchial asthma (BA) in school-age children and to develop effective correction methods.

Materials and Methods.

A total of 42 children aged 6–14 years suffering from BA were examined. The main group consisted of 31 children with BA, while the control group included 13 healthy children. To study the autonomic nervous system (ANS), the cardiointervalography (CIG) method was used to assess baseline autonomic tone

(BAT) and autonomic reactivity (AR). CIG is a non-specific method for evaluating adaptive-compensatory reactions.

Results.

Upon admission, 94.4% of children with BA exhibited a hyper-sympathicotonic baseline autonomic tone (BAT), 1.9% had a sympathicotonic BAT, and 3.7% had an initial eutonia. The majority of BA patients had a hyper-sympathicotonic BAT, indicating activation of sympatho-adrenal compensatory mechanisms. The presence of eutonia in a small subset of patients did not indicate a lack of ANS reaction. Clinical symptom analysis in these patients revealed simultaneous activity of both sympathetic and parasympathetic divisions of the ANS, leading to the detection of eutonia on CIG. A follow-up assessment of BAT after treatment, during clinical recovery, showed a relative normalization of the studied parameters: eutonia was found in 8.3% of cases, sympathicotonic BAT in 12.5%, and hyper-sympathicotonic BAT in 79.2% of children with BA. However, BAT data still indicated a pronounced tendency towards hyper-sympathicotonia, signifying continued tension in adaptive mechanisms during this disease period. Cardiointervalographic studies, which included calculations of the IN_2/IN_1 coefficient and determination of autonomic reactivity (AR), revealed that upon admission, normotonia was present in 7.4% of BA patients, hyper-sympathicotonic AR in 55.6%, and asympathicotonic AR in 37.0%. The study results indicate that during exacerbations of BA, children experience a significant increase in hyper-sympathicotonic AR frequency, accompanied by a decrease in normo-sympathicotonic AR, reflecting maximum autonomic function stress. An increase in asympathicotonic AR suggests exhaustion of compensatory sympathoadrenal mechanisms, likely associated with adaptive process failure. These children were more susceptible to intercurrent diseases, and their hospitalization duration was statistically significantly longer.

Conclusion.

Thus, the distribution of autonomic reactivity types in children with BA during exacerbations, compared to healthy children, was characterized by an increased frequency of hyper-sympathicotonic and asympathicotonic AR. The obtained results indicate excessive excitation of adaptive-compensatory reactions in the sympathetic division of the ANS, followed by their exhaustion. During remission, hyper-sympathicotonic reactivity remained the most prevalent, while asympathicotonic and normal AR were observed less frequently. This indicates a depletion of the protective mechanisms of the ANS.